

A STUDY ON EXPORT PERFORMANCE OF HOME TEXTILE PRODUCTS IN SPECIAL REFERENCE TO COIMBATORE

P. Gnanasekar* & D. Nithilan**

Sri Ramakrishna College of Arts & Science, Coimbatore, Tamilnadu

Cite This Article: P. Gnanasekar & D. Nithilan, "A Study on Export Performance of Home Textile Products in Special Reference to Coimbatore", International

Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Modern Education, Volume 4, Issue 1, Page Number 87-90, 2018.

Copy Right: © IJMRME, R&D Modern Research Publication, 2018 (All Rights Reserved). This is an Open Access Article distributed under the Creative Commons Attribution License, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium provided the original work is properly cited.

Abstract:

Home Fashion is an exclusive destination for home furnishings and decor items that combine top-of-the-line quality and affordability. The usages of home textile materials have increased recently as the living style of people have changed to more modern way of life. Unlike old times people recently have started to decorate their home with lots of decorative items which is majorly of home textiles. From the bed lines to table line a window blinds everything comes under home textiles. So the market is huge and the opportunities are very high. Since the market is new to our country people have less knowledge over it and they have not started to give their interest for this business. The people who have started their business in home textiles are facing troubles as the raw materials they get and the limited technology they use makes the product price very high. When these are exported the buyers abroad feel these items costly as the products in their country are comparatively cheap. So our people have to reduce the profit ratio and sell the products. Sometimes they even have to face a minor loss in few products as they have to keep continuing the relationship with the buyers. Governments can improve the subsidies and schemes and create awareness to people regarding this business so that this business sector can boom and earn more revenue to the country.

Key Words: Opportunities, Technology & Government

Introduction:

Now textile engineering study is becoming more demand-able then before. Because textiles have not only used for wearing but also hugely used in different sectors like technical textiles. Many research works are being done on textiles. We have entered a new age of experimentation at retail, with an assortment of prototypes and new concepts opening in the coming months. You can take it as sign retailers are feeling comfortable enough with the economy to begin testing new formulas. Or you could consider it an attempt by decades-old retailers to come up with something new.

Bed Bath & Beyond:

The Chelsea store in Manhattan is constantly in flux, but the big new thing opening there this month is a World Market home furnishings shop. Know what's even bigger and potentially cooler? The 100,000-sq.-ft. store BBB is setting up in Sunset Park, Brooklyn. When it opens next year, it will house four BBB nameplates in one location: Bed Bath & Beyondbuy Baby, Cost plus World Market, and Harmon Face Values.

Target Urban Express:

First opened in Minneapolis' Dinky town commercial neighbourhood a year ago this month, the small-format concept is geared to urban professionals. Two more recently opened on the West Coast (the San Francisco Financial District and Berkeley, Calif.). As seen on popsugar.com, the merchandise is grab-and-go: salads and sandwiches, accessories an office worker might need in a pinch (necklaces, ties, and socks), phone accessories, iPads, and desk basics (picture frames, coffee mugs, notebooks). Target is opening six more this year, including Chicago, Washington DC, San Diego, and St. Paul, Minn.

Objectives:

- ✓ To analyze the export performance of home textile products
- ✓ To analyze the technology installed in manufacturing the home textiles products
- ✓ To understand various schemes that government provide for home textile industry
- ✓ To offer suggestions findings and conclusions

Issues of Home Textiles:

The textile industry occupies a unique place in the country. It accounts for fourteen percent of the total industrial production contributes to nearly thirty percent of the total exports and in the second largest employment generator after agriculture. It provides direct employment to about thirty five million people and to another fifty million in allied areas. It means that one out of every six Indians is linked to the textile sector. An initiative of Corporate Social Responsibility activities in Textile industries are focused on environment protection, employees welfare, society development activities and company development. The textile industry in general usually assumes that responsible sourcing methods will result in high cost, particularly for labour, consumers, suppliers and top level management through environment protection and society development. The

present study attempts to analyse the development of textile industry based on CSR practices in selected districts of Tamil Nadu state.

Research Methodology:

Research is defined as human activity based on the intellectual application in the investigation of matter. The primary purpose for applied research is discovering, interpreting, and the development of the methods and systems for the advancement of human knowledge on a wide variety of scientific matters of our world and the universe. Research methodology is a way to systematically solve the research problem.

Research Design:

It is a conceptual structure with which research would be conducted. The study was descriptive in nature.

Descriptive Research:

The descriptive research describes attitude, perceptions, characteristics, activities, and situations. This type of research builds off from previous information, shows a relationship between variables, uses representative samples, has a structured research plan, is expensive, and conclusive.

Area of Study:

The study has been conducted in Vinson Home Fashions in Coimbatore

Data Collection:

Primary data as well as secondary data was used for data collection.

Primary Data:

The data collected by the researcher himself/herself is referred to a primary data. In this study the primary data were collected from Vinson home fashions manufacturer exporter in Coimbatore.

Secondary Data:

The data collected from already existing sources is known as the secondary data. The secondary data for this project was collected from journals and websites.

Scaling Technique Used:

Trend Analysis:

A trend analysis is an aspect of technical analysis that tries to predict the future movement of a stock based on past data. Trend analysis is based on the idea that what has happened in the past gives traders an idea of what will happen in the future. There are three main types of trends: short-, intermediate- and long-term.

Using Trend Analysis:

In order to begin analysing applicable data, it is necessary to first determine which market segment will be analysed. An example of sectors can include a focus on a particular industry, such as the automotive or pharmaceuticals sector, as well as a particular type of investment, such as the bond market once the sector has been selected; it is possible to examine the general performance of the sector. This can include how the sector was affected by internal and external forces. For example changes in a similar industry or the creation of a new governmental regulation would qualify as forces impacting the market. Analysts then take this data and attempt to predict the direction the market will take moving forward

SWOT Analysis:

A SWOT analysis (alternatively SWOT matrix) is a structured planning method used to evaluate the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats involved in a project or in a business venture. A SWOT analysis can be carried out for a product, place, industry or person. It involves specifying the objective of the business venture or project and identifying the internal and external factors that are favourable and unfavourable to achieve that objective.

- ✓ Strengths: characteristics of the business or project that give it an advantage over others.
- ✓ Weaknesses: characteristics that place the business or project at a disadvantage relative to others
- ✓ Opportunities: elements that the project could exploit to its advantage
- ✓ Threats: elements in the environment that could cause trouble for the business or project

Limitation of the Study:

- ✓ The study is conducted only in Coimbatore.
- ✓ The study is conducted within a limited period.
- ✓ The study was taken from the manufacturer and exporter point of view.

Analysis and Interpretation:

Export Performance of Bed Line Fabric Trend Percentage:

Year	Sales	Trend Percentage
12 -13	1000	100%
13 – 14	1500	150%
14 – 15	1800	180%
15 – 16	2000	200%
16 – 17	3000	300%

Interpretation:

The Trend Percentage calculated on the Export performance of Bed line fabric shows that compared to the base year 2012-13, there has been 50% increase in the year 2013-14, 80% increase in the year 2014-15, 100% increase in 2015-16 and 300% increase in the year 2016-17. This shows a drastic increase in the turnover over the years as far as bed line fabric is concerned.

Export Performance of Table Line Fabric:

Year	Sales	Trend Percentages
12 -13	1000	100%
13 – 14	3000	300%
14 – 15	2000	200%
15 – 16	2500	250%
16 – 17	30000	300%

Interpretation:

The Trend Percentage calculated on the Export performance of table line fabric shows that compared to the base year 2012-13, there has been 300% increase in the year 2013-14, 100 % decrease in the year 2014-15, 50% increase in 2015-16 and 300% increase in the year 2016-17. This shows a drastic increase in the turnover over the years as far as bed line fabric is concerned.

Export Performance of Kitchen Line Fabric:

Year	Sales	Trend Percentages
12 -13	2000	100%
13 – 14	2000	100%
14 – 15	4000	200%
15 – 16	6500	325%
16 – 17	7000	350%

Interpretation:

The Trend Percentage calculated on the Export performance of kitchen line fabric shows that compared to the base year 2012-13, there has been level of the previous year 2013-14, 100% increase in the year 2014-15, 125% increase in 2015-16 and 350% increase in the year 2016-17. This shows a drastic increase in the turnover over the years as far as bed line fabric is concerned.

Export Performance of Towel Line Fabric:

Year	Sales	Trend Percentages
12 -13	1000	100%
13 – 14	2000	200%
14 – 15	4000	400%
15 – 16	12500	1250%
16 – 17	10500	1050%

Interpretation:

The Trend Percentage calculated on the Export performance of towel line fabric shows that compared to the base year 2012-13, there has been 100% increase in the year 2013-14, 200% increase in the year 2014-15, 850% increase in 2015-16 and 200% decrease in the year 2016-17. This shows a drastic decrease in the turnover over the years as far as bed line fabric is concerned.

Export Performance of Cushions and Throws Fabric:

Year	Sales	Trend Percentages
12 -13	6000	100
13 – 14	5000	83
14 – 15	2000	33
15 – 16	2500	42
16 – 17	3000	50

Interpretation:

The Trend Percentage calculated on the Export performance of cushions and throws fabric shows that compared to the base year 2012-13, there has been 17% decrease in the year 2013-14, 50% decrease in the year 2014-15, 9% increase in 2015-16 and 7% increase in the year 2016-17. This shows a drastic increase in the turnover over the years as far as bed line fabric is concerned.

Findings:

- ✓ Majority 300% of the respondents are between the bed line fabric of [2016 – 17] years
- ✓ Majority 300% of the respondents are between the table line fabric of [2013 – 14] [2016 – 17] years
- ✓ Majority 350% of the respondents are between the kitchen line fabric of [2016 – 17] years
- ✓ Majority 1250% of the respondents are between the towel line fabric of [2015 – 16] years
- ✓ Majority 100% of the respondents are between the bed line fabric of [2012 – 13] years

Suggestions:

- ✓ The cost of the products can be reduced by technological upgradation
- ✓ Low-cost and quality products should be manufactured in India because that's what we lag from our competitors
- ✓ Government policies can be improved which is very low for home textiles industry in India
- ✓ Government can provide more schemes and subsidy for export of products
- ✓ Customers abroad expect more quality of products. So we have to improve our technology and purchase quality raw materials.
- ✓ As only 2% of consumers say home textiles are their favourite item to shop for, they will likely spend their discretionary money elsewhere, if their value expectations are not being met.
- ✓ In order to meet or exceed projected sales growth in the home textiles market, retailers and brands must understand consumers' expectations, the issues that negatively impact customer loyalty, and develop tactics to solve reported issues.

Conclusion:

The people who have started their business in home textiles are facing troubles as the raw materials they get and the limited technology they use makes the product price very high. When these are exported the buyers abroad feel these items costly as the products in their country are comparatively cheap. So our people have to reduce the profit ratio and sell the products. Sometimes they even have to face a minor loss in few products as they have to keep continuing the relationship with the buyers. Governments can improve the subsidies and schemes and create awareness to people regarding this business so that this business sector can boom and earn more revenue to the country.

References:

1. The Handloom Weavers: A Study in the Cotton Industry during the Industrial - D. Bythell
2. Development of Handloom Industry, Organization, Production, - Dr. Nagen
3. Economics of Handloom Industry - M. Lakshmi Narsaiah
4. www.indiastat.com
5. www.textilesintelligence.com
6. www.fibre2fashion.com